

EIC User Group Newsletter

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NEWS

- Plans for the **EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Studies** have been drafted by the Steering Committee and have been presented both in the IB meeting of Oct. 10th and in the UG quarterly meeting of Oct. 24th. The purpose is to advance the state of documented physics studies and detector concepts in preparation for the EIC, as well as to provide a basis for further development of concepts for experimental equipment best suited for science needs, including complementarity of two detectors. EIC activities at DOE seem to be proceeding fast, thus the plan is to finalize these studies in approximately 1 year by putting together a Yellow-Report-like document which constitutes input towards future Technical Design Reports (TDR). The approach consists in forming two Working Groups (WG), one for Physics requirements and one for Detector concepts, with 4 conveners each. Each WG will be structured in several sub-groups, with 2/3 conveners per sub-group. The timeline schedule is:
 - 12-13 December 2019, MIT: Kick-off organizational meeting
 - 19-21 March 2021, Temple Univ. - Philadelphia: 1st Workshop
 - 22-24 May 2020, Univ. Pavia - Pavia (Italy): 2nd Workshop
 - 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C.: 3rd Workshop
 - 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley: 4th WorkshopFurther details about the draft can be found here:
https://www.dropbox.com/s/p27hc9ywfata2ws/Rolf_EICUG_Quarterly_Mtg_102419_YR_plans_v4.pptx?dl=0

- The EIC User Group is **growing!** Since the last Summer meeting in Paris, new Institutions joined the community:
 Memorial University of Newfoundland (Canada)
 IIT Patna (India)
 Universidad de Alcala (Spain)
 Pennsylvania State University Berks (USA)
 Davidson College (USA)
 Institute for Nonperturbative Physics at Nanjing University (China)
 Pusan National University (South Korea).
 As of Oct. 31st, we have 967 members from 194 institutions in 30 countries.
- The Briefing Book of the 2020 European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (**ESPPU**) is now public and can be found at the link <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2691414> . The EIC is mentioned in several places, in particular in Sec. 4.3.
- Results of the recent **survey on EICUG request of information** have been discussed in the recent quarterly meeting on Oct. 24th. Details can be found at this link https://www.dropbox.com/s/c88aieeztco2euu/7_BerndSurov-Survey-EICUG-Remote-Meeting-10242019.pdf?dl=0

NEWS from the EICUG SOFTWARE WORKING GROUP

The short-term goal of the software working group is to meet in FY20 the requirements for common simulation tools and documentation for the EICUG. Fast simulation tools for the EIC are available. A quick start tutorial can be found on the website for EIC Software:

<https://eic.gitlab.io/documents/quickstart/>

The current work focusses on a common Geant4 infrastructure for the EIC that allows geometry exchange between the eRHIC and JLEIC concepts.

Important Links

- Mailing list: eicug-software@eicug.org
- Repository: <http://gitlab.com/eic>
- Website: <https://software.eicug.org>

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- For **upcoming conferences** and workshops see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> . For a list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from ELECTION and NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The term of Ernst Sichtermann as “At Large Member” of the EICUG Steering Committee ended on Oct. 31 2019. It has been extended to Dec. 31st in order to coordinate elections in January and/or July of each year, as needed. Nominations have been called for with deadline Oct. 31 and **elections** will be run during November 2019.

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

[EIC ad-hoc meeting on detector and physics simulations](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 10 July 2019

[EIC User Group meeting 2019](#), Paris (France), 22-26 July 2019

[27th International Nuclear Physics Conference \(INPC 2019\)](#), Glasgow (Scotland), 28 July - 2 August 2019

[29th Conference on Lepton and Photon Interactions \(LP2019\)](#), Toronto (Canada), 5-10 August 2019

[Hadron 2019](#), Guilin (China), 16-21 August 2019

[8th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 19\)](#), Kolymbari (Greece), 21-30 August 2019

[The 11th Circum-Pan-Pacific Symposium on High Energy Spin Physics](#), Miyazaki (Japan), 27-30 August 2019

[POETIC 2019](#), Berkeley (CA - USA), 16-20 September 2019

[Light Cone 2019](#), Palaiseau (France), 16-20 September 2019

[EIC Software meeting and GEANT4 Technical Forum](#), JLab Newport News (VA - USA), 24 September 2019

[13th European Research Conference on Electromagnetic Interactions with Nucleons and Nuclei](#), Paphos (Cyprus), 27 October - 2 November 2019

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

[CHEP 2019](#), Adelaide (Australia), 3-8 November 2019

[Quark Matter 2019](#), Wuhan (China), 4-8 November 2019

[EIC Streaming Readout workshop](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[LPC Workshop on Physics Connections the LHC and EIC](#), FermiLab (IL - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[Forward Physics and QCD at LHC](#), Guanajuato (Mexico), 18-23 November 2019

[MCEGs for future ep and eA facilities](#), Vienna (Austria), 20-22 November 2019

[Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2019\)](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 November 2019

[CPAD Instrumentation Frontier Workshop](#), Madison (WI - USA), 8-10 December 2019

[International workshop on QCD with EIC \(QEIC\)](#), Bombay (India), 4-7 January 2020

[EIC Detector R&D Committee Meeting](#), Upton (NY - US), 30-31 January 2020

[2020 Santa Fe Jets and Heavy Flavor Workshop](#), Santa Fe (NM - US), 3-5 February 2020

[Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2020

[KEK Workshop on Femtotechnologies by quantum computers 2020](#), Tsukuba (Japan), 7 March 2020

[DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY - USA), 23-27 March 2020

[Rencontres de Moriond, QCD and high-energy interactions](#), La Thuile (Italy), 28 March - 4 April 2020

[QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - USA), 27 April - 1 May 2020

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 1-6 June 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 30 July - 5 August 2020

EIC Users Group Meeting 2020, Miami (F - USA), 3-7 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24 September 2021

Please, have a look also at the following links:

<http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming>

<http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html>